

GROUP BASED RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND PRICING MODEL IN CLOUD COMPUTING

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ABSTRACT

Cloud computing utilizes large scale computing infrastructure that has been radically changing the IT landscape enabling remote access to computing resources with low service cost, high scalability, availability and accessibility. Serving tasks from multiple users where the tasks are of different characteristics with variation in the requirement of computing power may cause under or over utilization of resources. Therefore maintaining such mega-scale datacenter requires efficient resource management procedure to increase resource utilization. However, while maintaining efficiency in service provisioning it is necessary to ensure the maximization of profit for the cloud providers. Most of the current research works aims at how providers can offer efficient service provisioning to the user and improving system performance. There are comparatively fewer specific works regarding resource management which also deals with the economic section that considers profit maximization for the provider. In this paper we represent a model that deals with both efficient resource utilization and pricing of the resources. The joint resource management model combines the work of user assignment, task scheduling and load balancing on the fact of CPU power endorsement. We propose four algorithms respectively for user assignment, task scheduling, load balancing and pricing that works on group based resources offering reduction in task execution time(56.3%), activated physical machines(41.44%), provisioning cost(23%) . The cost is calculated over a time interval involving the number of served customer at this time and the amount of resources used within this time.

KEYWORDS

Resource Management, Resource Pricing, Task Execution, Load Balancing, Task Scheduling.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing is a pool of virtual machines with underlying datacenters or physical machines providing various kinds of agile and effective services to the user in a form of virtualization of every kind of computing services from infrastructure to software[1] [2]. With the development in Internet uses of Internet enabled devices are increasing day by day in fact the number of IoT enabled devices have already outnumbered total human population[3]. This results in more generation of large scale data which requires faster processing and faster task response. Therefore more devices are now getting connected to the cloud as these devices are limited to storage and processing power. However with the increase in users cloud service providers are now more compelled to use larger and powerful datacenters as investments were done by many telecommunication companies in order to satisfy their growing customer requirements and avoiding any SLA violation[4]. These datacenters are equipped with powerful hardware and connected with high bandwidth networks and managed with software resources. As a result the requirement of efficient management procedures for handling such large datacenters are becoming a topic of interest to the researchers. Current research works mostly aims at better service provisioning to the user and improving system performance with only some specific works

regarding economic and costing model. These models deal with the resource management in cloud computing which assure efficient resource management that ensures maximization of profit for the provider. As Both user and providers play important role in shaping of cloud computing with clear and distinct promising features, resource management procedure that holds the end of the bargain for both users and providers are important.

Figure 1: Cost based price management in cloud computing

Resource management in cloud covers a number of issues such as efficient task scheduling, resource provisioning, resource allocation, resource adaption, tasks assignment, load balancing and others. Among them three important features of resource management can be considered resource scheduling, load balancing and task assignment to shape the resource utilization in cloud environment. Resource scheduling refers to a timetable of events maintaining events and resources to determine the time an activity is assigned to execution. Load balancing aims to evenly distributing tasks over physical machines to reduce traffic in any particular ones and to maximize the number of machines in stand by mode to reduce power usage. Tasks assignment aims to mapping tasks to a VM and generally chooses the VM where it can execute faster. The provisioning and placement of VMs must be done efficiently taking into account the available resources in cloud. Again, the reconfigurations must be performed fast to resize or release the existing virtual resources because of the variability and elasticity of resource demand [5]. Inefficient resource management negatively affects performance and cost as well as impairing system functionality.

Ensuring Profit for every cloud provider is a fundamental goal. Traditional procedures such as system optimization tends to aim at different system performance metrics based on system parameters and constraints rather than economic factors (the profit, cost, and revenue) [5]. A cost based model calculates the price of a service using all over cost for providing the service as well as adding a percentage of the cost as desired profit [5][6]. This model uses 1. fixed cost and 2. variable cost to calculate the total cost [5]. Fixed cost includes cost required for setting up hardware, servers and network devices, required human resources. On the other hand variable cost is not constant, it varies according to the number of sales produced by the service such as energy, bandwidth, cost of transferring data between different datacenters and so on. Providers use cost based pricing for large scale datacenters to calculate the cost for a service for the incoming users tasks requests [7].

Resources in a cloud server includes both hardware and software. Cloud computing infrastructure is generally hosted on datacenters and these datacenters can be geographically distributed and connected using high speed network. A hypervisor software emulates server's CPU, memory, network and other resources to enable isolation of multiple users when running on the same physical machine. Tasks generated from user devices are assigned to virtual machines with cloud broker. Tasks handled by a server are of hybrid in nature where some tasks require more computation power than others and again they can differ in priorities. IaaS-Clouds offer VMs at a specific monetary cost. Excess consumption of virtual resources need to be avoided as underutilized worker-nodes reduce the monetary value the cloud client achieves. The number of serving VMs must never surpass the threshold over which excess VMs become an overhead for power consumption. Therefore assigning tasks to VMs to ensure both faster execution and better utilization of resources at the same time is a tricky issue as during service provisioning the provider have to maintain both Quality of Service (QoS) and gaining the maximum revenue.

In this paper we have identified efficient resource management with profit maximization raises three important issues-1. What types of tasks are needed to assign 2. How datacenters should place the tasks for execution on VMs, 3. How to reduce the number of active servers at a datacenter along with serving maximum numbers of users, 4. How the users are priced so that providers can have maximized profit. In this research we answer the questions by modeling a resource management system and use cost based pricing model to calculate the price of resources used. In our proposed model we logically divide the computing resources in a datacenter into groups called Resource Group based on what type of tasks will be assigned to them. A number of VMs are assigned to each group where VMs within same group are assigned to execute tasks of requiring similar amount of computing power. Tasks assignment and scheduling works in a sequential manner. Four different algorithms are presented which works to achieve a overall profit for the provider and faster task execution for the user.

In the rest part of this article we have described some scenarios of resource management and pricing in cloud in Section 2. After that we have represented our proposed system architecture in Section 3 and algorithms for task assignment, task scheduling and load balancing in Section 4. Later we have evaluated our proposed method with some other existing ones presented in section 5.

2. RELATED WORKS

There are several works regarding resource management in cloud computing. Different costing models have been proposed for pricing the services. However there are very few research which collaborates cost management with resource management in cloud computing. The management service observes mechanisms in the virtual servers within the cloud computing sessions which allows it to monitor, analyse as well as provide reports along with alerting pertaining to performance metrics of the various virtual servers [8]. In [9] authors proposed an energy efficient adaptive resource management for vehicular cloud to maximize the overall communication and computing energy efficiency. It meets the application-induced hard QoS requirements with least transmission rates but with maximum delays and delay-jitters. In [10] author gave their concern on network visualization of resource allocation dynamically in cloud computing and the importance of meeting QoS. When the best effort falls then the Service Level Agreement (SLA) takes the equivalent actions. Besides different scheduling and load balancing algorithm has been proposed [11][12][13][14]. In [15] researchers proposed to schedule the tasks based on requirement of computation power and [14] represented a load balancing mechanism also based on power requirement. Authors in [16] proposed a resource utilization method based on greedy method. According to [17][18][19] when using mobile devices augmented with cloudlets for capacity increment the offered service to load ratio is needed to be considered. These research works considers only limited constraints rather than a complete scenario of resource management.

Besides how providing resource efficiency affects providers revenue is not discussed which affects in long term provisioning.

Various model for pricing cloud service have been proposed for cloud market scenario e.g costbased pricing [7][20][21] depicts how the cost of the resources used can be calculated, profit maximization [22][23] aiming for increasing profit of the provider, differential pricing [24][15] charges different price to different client based on their demand. According to [2] charges for the service request are decided by the costing mechanism depending on the time of submission, rate of pricing or the availability of resource and accounting mechanism is used for calculation of the actual usage of resources. A detailed overview of cloud resource management using economic analysis is given in [5]. Techno-economic modelling is used in [20] to assess the cost efficiency of using SDN into the LTE network. According to [21] Particularly for most demand side management applications because of the variability of customer behaviours, the computing requirements fluctuates significantly which discourages providers for setting up new datacenters. The seemingly never-ending resources of a physical cloud, exacting the specific amount of resources required must be based on both the consumer's intended amount of expenditure and the performance bottlenecks which can be visible only at runtime [22]. They propose to continuously monitoring user application performance and removing or adding VMs when performance fluctuations is observed in serving the needs of autonomous systems. To maximize the profit, a cloud provider needs to understand both service charges and business costs as well as the way they are by the characteristics of the applications and the configuration of a multi-server system [23]. Pricing also differs based on the geo-distribution of datacenters. A dynamic pricing along with profit maximization aiming pricing in geographically distributed datacenters in cloud is proposed in [25].

3. RESOURCE GROUP MODELING

In this research work we propose that the resources are divided into groups. According to what services the provider is offering the groups are created based on the requirement of both the provider and the user. For example let's think a cloud provider has N geographically distributed datacenters. Based on the job type tasks are divided in three groups where they differ in their requirement of computation power. Based on this the datacenter resources can be divided into three groups. Each group contains a number of VMs and the groups are further divided into subgroups. Our proposed model partitions all the server resources based on the CPU power required which implies the number of CPU cycles and the amount of internal memory the groups are assigned. The grouping is done logically which implies that they don't necessarily have to be physically separated.

3.1 Resource Group

A Resource Group is like a logical container that has a certain amount of computing resource assigned to them. Provider can deploy, manage and monitor all the resources for provisioning solution as a group, rather than handling these resources individually. The groups can be divided into subgroups when required. A sequential approach is followed in deploying and balancing the resources. Large group of resources are again divided into subgroups. Groups are different with one another on the basis of amount of resource consumption. Let's the provider's resources in a datacenter is divided into two groups A and B. Group A is for servicing users demanding a large amount of power and the other one is for the less demanding. The first group offers instances that is constituted of more numbers of CPU and more Powerful (Speed, MIPS) CPU and RAM power than the second group. As the larger groups are split into smaller subgroups control becomes more distributed. The assignment, scheduling, load balancing algorithms work differently on this subgroups and synchronizes when required. The subgroups contain a certain number of VMs. Each VM is assigned to user tasks according to their demand. An array is used to contain identification and status of this VMs at a certain time. Within this array the VMs offers a

sequential relation andrelativity among VMs that belongs to the same group. The resources in each subgroup is offeredas instances. For simplifying our description each instance will be addressed as a PM. Resourcesare sharable among the groups. But the sharing should be minimized. A datacenter has ResourceGroup identified as A, B, C. . . .N where N=total number of General Group and threshold ofth1,th2,th3...th1 .Then incoming tasks can be grouped based on the threshold such as tasks requiring power below th1 are assigned to group A ,tasks between th1 and th2 are submitted to group B and goes on.Tasks in the same group need similar amount of computation power but largely differswith other groups but pretty similar within the same group. Subgroups are identified as followsand tasks in the subgroup are similar in requirement of power.A particular number of VMs areassigned to a subgroups , during task moving for load balancing or remapping VMs within samegroups are prioritized. Subgroup within each group= 0, 1, 2. n

Service point (VM) in group:

Group A – subgroup 0 VM=0, 1, 2. n

Group A – subgroup 1 VM=n+1, n+2. n+m

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Group A – subgroup x VM n+j, n+j+1. n+j+m

Similarly,

Group B – subgroup 0 VM=0, 1, 2. n

Group B – subgroup 1 VM=n+1, n+2. n+m

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.....

Group B – subgroup x VM n+j, n+j+1. n+j+m

and so on.

Here,n+j =value ID 1 increments than last one in the previous subgroup

A flag indicates if a subgroup is full or not

3.2 Group Based Resource Management

The resource management procedure has different portion that works together for a better cost efficient management of the servers. This system uses Energy efficient management of IaaS[15] cloud which is a integrated approach for VM migration and reconfiguration, and PM power management and Task Scheduling algorithm in Cloud Computing Environment Based on Cloud Pricing models and [28] ,as a base for our algorithms to offer a better load balancing and resource utilization based on resource intensity aware load balancing . The different portion is responsible for different managing work in resource management.

- **Access Log:** The access log is responsible for ensuring the authenticity of the user request.
- **Assignment Manager:** The assignment manager is responsible for assigning user to a freeservice node which in this case will be a VM.It ensures easy identification and servicing ofthe user at that VM as this ID’s maintains a sequence accordance with their group.
- **Scheduler:**The scheduler is responsible for assigning a PM which represents an instanceof the resources that is required by the user task. The PM assignment to a VM depends onwhich group they are assigned in. It programs a VM migration to other group when there isnot enough resource in the group.
- **Load Statistics:** This portion check for load in each VM and eventually in each group. This counts the load as percentage of the total resources assigned and the amount occupied. This uses a threshold power to determine if this group can have any new users or new PM could be assigned to avoid any collusion.

- **Predictor:** The predictor gives an estimation on if there is any possibility of conflict and hunger among users can happen.
- **Pricing and revenue:** Calculates the price for the user .Also shows price that the user will find if they use some new resources. With the provider’s input in each groups cost the revenue portion calculates the monthly revenue from a particular group which is calculated as per subgroup.

Figure 2: Group based resource management

3.3.Resource Grouping and Profit maximization

The cloud service provider’s actual profit refers to the difference between the revenue and the costs[23].To maximize service providers’ profits and ensure load balancing within them, each cloud provider determines the in-sourcing price as well as the available quota of resources based on which group the serving resources are resided.The pricing policy proposed in this paper uses the insourcing price which is set according to the VM costs for a certain type of tasks.Different group has different price calculated within a timing interval.Groups with lower power has lower price and higher power requiring groups has price set based on the type of resources assigned to them.According to cost based pricing model services are priced depending on the resources consumed.Therefore each user task in this model is priced based on the group they are assigned to.As a result different tasks can get easily priced based on their power requirement rather than having a common price calculated over time.The proposed constraints ensures that only limited number of PMs are activated and at the same time tasks are having low average waiting time in the queue.Grouping and subgrouping of resources ensures evenly distribution of resources among the executing tasks hence reducing under or over consumption of

computing power. This reduces the overall provisioning cost and increasing the gross profit for the service provider.

4. GROUP BASED RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND PRICING

This section describes how Resource group model is applied for different aspects of resource management which includes task assignment, task scheduling, load balancing along with pricing of provisioning resources. Different algorithms have been designed for each section along with necessary constraints.

4.1. Task Assignment

This section depicts how tasks are assigned to different resource group. The main idea of the enhanced algorithm is allocating the particular VM to the requested tasks according to the following steps:- At first the required computation power of each VM is calculated based on the total number of MIPS allocated to it. Calculate the processing power of each VM_i (i.e., VM_i 's Total MIPS) using equation (1)

$$Total_MIPS[i] = CPUs * MIPS \quad (1)$$

CPUs= the number of cores, MIPS=million instruction per second of the single core of the VM. Here $i=0, 1, 2, \dots$, represents the position of the subgroup. Then calculate the required power of each task of all the received tasks from the user using equation (2). If the waiting task has no of 'p' type of tasks then

$$Task_p^m = \frac{\sum_{ts=1}^m MIPS_n}{m} \quad (2)$$

Different threshold values are determined for different groups. Tasks are assigned to the group which matches with its power requirement. Such as for group A if a task of type p requires MIPS such that $MIPS_p(i) < Threshold_A$, it's assigned to group A. Therefore all m tasks of type p will be assigned to Group A after inspecting which subgroups to choose.

An array is used to offer the server nodes in a group. Then using equation (2) it is determined if there is enough resources even if there is a free node. A Time threshold T_{low_con} =Low power consumption for time t refers if a node is consuming a very low server power (low-con) for a certain time T then the VM should be transferred to low power consumption group to avoid wastage and vice versa for time T_{high_con} =High Power Consumption for time t

According to the calculations the following algorithm is designed for assignment of the tasks waiting in the queue for execution with considering the power requirement .

Algorithm 1: Task Assignment algorithm

-
1. **procedure** Assignment(G; ts) //G groups, ts=tasks to be assigned
 2. Array[Service_node(ni)] //user assigned identification no
 3. Array[a][b]
 4. a = user_id
 5. Calculate MIPS of all p type of tasks
 6. **for** j = 0 to total_numberof_groups **do** //determining the required group
 7. Compare Power of Task_p with group threshold
 8. **for all** subgroups in group G **do**
 9. **if** (**then** load_in_subgroup > T_{safe_load})
 10. choose group G
 11. **else** Wait in the queue

12. **end if**
13. **end for**
14. **end for**
15. Check for the next request
16. **end procedure**

4.2. Task Scheduling

After selecting a group the tasks are needed to assign to a VM contained within a subgroup. Power factor of each VM of a subgroup x is calculated as follows-

$$PF \text{ of VM, VM}[i]_{PF} = \frac{Total_{MIPS}[i] - inuse_{MIPSi}}{Total_{MIPS}[i]} \quad (3)$$

Power factor of each subgroup is calculated using equation (4) which defines the credibility of each subgroup

$$PF \text{ of subgroups, subgrp}[n]_{PF} = \sum_{q=s}^e \frac{Total_{MIPS}[q] - inuse_{MIPSq}}{Total_{MIPS}[q]} \quad (4)$$

Here, n=no of subgroup, s=first VM in the nth subgroup and e=last VM in nth subgroup. If PF of a subgroup is greater than x the subgroup is not eligible for new task scheduling. Rather than searching each VM separately for eligibility this mechanism allows a group of VMs to be identified at a time which reduces the time cost for searching suitable VM. Tasks are sorted according to their priority in the waiting queue. Required power is calculated for the task with equation (2) and its power factor is calculated using equation (5).

$$Task[ts]_{PF} = \frac{Task_p^m}{VM[i]} \quad (5)$$

Search the requested subgroup sequentially to find a VM that provides processing power equal to or less than the power factor of the task by considering that the difference between the selected tasks processing power and VM to be minimum.

Algorithm 2: Task Scheduling Algorithm

- 1: **procedure** Scheduler(n,ts)
- 2: **for** i = 0 to m **do**
- 3: Define MIPS of the VMs
- 4: Calculate the power factor of each VM
- 5: **end for**
- 6: **for** i = 0 to ndo
- 7: Define MIPS of the subgroups
- 8: Calculate power factor of each subgroup
- 9: **end for**
- 10: **for** i = 0 to m **do**
- 11: Calculate the PF of each task
- 12: Choose the VM with which task have the highest power factor VM_i
- 13: allotment = Task_{PF} * requested MIPS
- 14: **end for**
- 15: **end procedure**

4.3. Load Balancing

Overloaded PM transfers VMs running on them which have high consumption on high-power resources and limited consumption on low power resources. Therefore it relieves its load quickly at the same time completely utilizing datacenter resources. Selected PM generally has high competence on the high intensity resources for actively tend to ignore overloading destination PMs in the future. In our work task allocation and VM allocation works based on communication rate. Communication rate refers to the number of contacts between the source VM and destination VM in a unit time period. Communication rate T_{xi} (VM_i of subgroup x) for a VM_{ni} with its local VM_{kh} (VM_h of any subgroup k) is denoted by,

$$T_{xi} \sum_{i=1}^n T_{xikh} \quad (6)$$

$k=x$ if the two communicating VM are in the same group. Task re-allocation takes place within the same subgroup whereas VM re-allocation occurs among different groups. When VMs and tasks are reallocated the performance degrades [27]. We aim to minimize the degradation. To reduce the degradation the number of switches in the communication path need to be lessened. Reallocation depends on the results of equation (6) and (7) as follows Load of VM_i comparing with others in the same subgroup

$$L_{VM_i} = \frac{VM[i]_{PF}}{subgrp[n]_{PF}} \quad (7)$$

If $L_{VM_i} < \text{threshold}_{load}$ (minimum load: below this threshold is considered as low power consuming) then, tasks of VM_i is transmitted to VM_j where

$$L_{VM_j} = \min \left(\frac{VM[j]_{PF}}{VM[i]_{PF}} \right) \quad (8)$$

if VM_j has enough resources and has low communication rate with the transmitting VM otherwise it switches to next VM. Therefore the now free VM and its related PMs turned to stand by mode. Similarly if a subgroup is running low consuming VMs they are transferred to the subgroup with minimum communication cost. In our proposed method the number of switches is constrained by the number of VMs in a subgroup for tasks reallocation and number of subgroups for VM allocation. If one node is consuming more power its task is distributed. To distribute the task load free resources are at first searched within the group it belongs to. It ensures resource utilization and keeps more PM at standby mode. If a node A is consuming too much CPU power and the consecutive subgroup is already crossing its threshold then for further assignment the VM is transferred to the next subgroup that can take it.

Algorithm 3: Load balancing Algorithm

```

1: procedure load_balancing
2:   for i = 0 to ndo
3:     Check load in each subgroup
4:     if ( thenLoadinSubgroup[n] > Taccepted)
5:       while LoadinSubgroup[n] > Taccepted do
6:         Select the maximum power consumer i, k
7:         for each node in the subgroup do
8:           Calculate the communication rate with k
9:           Choose the VM with highest communication rate and low load
10:          Shift task to the chosen VM
11:        end for
12:      end while
13:    end if
14:    if LoadinSubgroup[n] < Taccepted_low then

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15:         Choose the nearest subgroup s in the array
16:         if s subgroup can support the load then
17:             Shift tasks to s
18:             n =standbymode
19:         end if
20:         elseChoose the next nearest subgroup
21:         endif
22:     end for
23: end procedure

```

4.4. Pricing and revenue

Pricing and revenue is calculated as per subgroup basis. Revenue is calculated as how much maintenance cost is implicated and how much gain is received. Pricing is done according to the usage of a particular group resources. VMs from high computational power costs higher price. Each group declares their price. Price for each task is calculated based on which groups the tasks will be assigned to according to their power requirement. Calculated price are then displayed to the customer. This optimization problem is for the cloud provider to choose an appropriate price for each type of jobs at each group ($p_n^p(t)$), the best number of servers to provision each type of VMs in each datacenter ($N_n^d(t)$), the optimal numbers of jobs of each type to schedule and to drop ($u_d^r(t)$) and $G_n^d(t)$, in each t at each datacenter, to maximize its time-averaged profit. The pricing at time t can be calculated as a optimized solution

$$P_n^p(t) = \sum u_d^r(t) * P_G(n) - G_h^d(t) \quad (9)$$

The constraint ($u_d^r(t) < i \in n$) ensures that the activated PMs for the tasks are within the same subgroup otherwise communication rate will decrease. Revenue for each datacenter is calculated as a factor of serving tasks at time t and the number of activated server. Using the cost based pricing model at time t the cost for serving a p type job is

$$C_p(t) = \sum u_d^r(t) * C_G(n) \quad (10)$$

The revenue for service provisioning at the end of time t (rev) is

$$R(t_{rev}) = \sum_{t=t_0}^{t=t_{rev}} \sum_{job=p}^{job=q} P_p^n(t) - C_p(t) \quad (11)$$

Number of activated PMs are constrained to a certain number which prevents unnecessary scheduling of tasks to new VMs. It enables provisioning most number of users with less number of activated server.

Algorithm 4: Pricing and revenue

```

1: Procedure pricing_revenue:
2: for each resource group G do
3: Determine the unit price for group G
4: Publish the price
5: end for
6: for each task do
7: Determine the Group
8: Choose the unit price
9: end for
10: for each resource group G do
11: Calculate the number of activated subgroups

```

- 12: **for** each activated subgroup in G **do**
- 13: from time t_0 to t_e
- 14: Calculate the price of the tasks serving in t_0 - t_e using (9)
- 15: Calculate the serving cost using unit price $C_G(n)$
- 16: Calculate revenue with(11)
- 17: **end for**
- 18: **end for**
- 19: **end procedure**

5. EVALUATION AND RESULT

To evaluate the efficiency of our proposed algorithm we develop a simulator strictly following the system model defined in this paper. The algorithms proposed here are programmed with Java programming language using Eclipse 4.5.0 Mars IDE. Two Different programs are written in Java where one is with resources divided in groups and one with resources without dividing in groups. The first group uses an Enumeration that contains 6 groups of variables with different number of CPU, MIPS, Memory as signed to it. We have compared our proposed model with different existing algorithms including Enhanced Power based Scheduling (EPBS) and Power intensity Load Balancing (PBLB) and others. The Amount of CPU power, runtime Cost and re-allocation cost is calculated. And With these values cost is calculated assigning random cost at values and compared with existing algorithms. The existing algorithm shows runtime complexity $((t - t_0) \log n)$ where t =starting time and t_0 =Finishing time and n =no of service node. In our proposed algorithm n reduces to n/k where k =number of groups. So the proposed algorithm's runtime complexity reduces to $((t - t_0)(n/k) \log(n/k) + k)$.

Figure 3. tasks vs task execution rate

Figure 4. tasks vs average waiting time in the queue

Figure 5. Tasks load vs power used

Figure 7. task vs task reallocation cost

Figure 6. Load vs activated PM number

Figure 8. user vs provisioning cost

The first figure compares the task execution rate of our proposed system against the server greedy and EPBS and has a gain of 56.3% over server greedy and of around 67% over EPBS. In figure(4) we see the average waiting time for a task to be served tend to have a steady nature for our proposed model comparing to EPBS with a gain of 38% lower average waiting time than EPBS. Figure(5) shows the power consumed by the server with varying load for round robin, first-fit, RIAL and our proposed system. With the increase of load power consumption increases at a high rate. In the proposed work the consumption of power is restricted by the structure of the subgroup so it has a lower power consumption rate comparing to the others (nearly 20% against first-fit, 40% against round-robin, 34% against RIAL) with the increase in load. It also shows around 41.44% of less activated number of PMs when the load increases (figure-6). In the last two figures (7) and (8) the cost for task reallocation and provisioning represents the proposed system's efficiency over existing models. Comparing with intensity based load management we find our proposed work has around 68% less reallocation cost. Again it can serve the same number of users for the same tasks with a reduction of 23% in the provisioning cost. This in turn results in the profit maximization for the service provider.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we propose a group based resource management and pricing model in cloud computing that logically divides the computing resources into groups, based on computation power requirement of heterogeneous tasks from various users. Dividing large datacenter into smaller groups enables better synchronization among them by reducing the task execution time, waiting time in the queue, power consumption and overall provisioning cost which in turn increases the revenue of a cloud provider. Assigning tasks into power-consumption based groups makes sure a high power consumer is never assigned to a low instance which may cause the excess abuse of power and similarly assignment of low power requiring tasks to high power servers never causes under-utilization of resources. In this grouping system tasks of all similar power-consumers belong to similar groups resulting in lower SLA violation. Our proposed model put constraints on PM assignment based on subgroups to keep minimum number of PMs activated and at the same time maximum number of user assignment. Simulation results show that our proposed algorithm outperforms existing systems in various aspects such as execution time, average task waiting time in the queue, used power, number of activated PMs, task reallocation cost and overall provisioning cost to a notable extent. We have achieved reduction in task execution time (56.3%), activated physical machines (41.44%), provisioning cost (23%) when comparing our system with existing models.

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